

Design Infrastructure: The Key to Australia's Economic & Social Development

Dr. Terence Love

© Copyright Terence Love 2002

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19675979

Abstract

Design activity is an essential aspect of the innovation and knowledge processes, which governments in Australia and other developed countries regard as the key to economic and social development. This paper sets out some key issues in the relationships between designing, design infrastructure, innovation, the development of knowledge-based economies, and the fulfilment of programs aimed at national economic and social development. The paper identifies significant weaknesses in Australia's design infrastructure. It analyses the ways that these weaknesses compromise Australian investments in innovation, research, education and business process change. The paper concludes with suggestions for organisational and funding initiatives aimed at addressing the weaknesses in Australia's design infrastructure to provide sufficient support to realise the intended outcomes of Australian programs -for economic and social development.

Introduction

Design activities form the practical core of innovation, have a key role in successful business processes and strategies, and are essential in gaining economic and social benefits from investments in research (see, for example, Commonwealth of Australia, 2001; Dept of Industry Science and Resources, 1999; Innovation Summit Implementation Group, 2000; Owen, 1990). Innovation and the building of knowledge-based economies are the main elements of developed nations' strategies for economic and social development (see, for example, Boardman, 2001; Commonwealth of Australia, 2001; Dept of Industry Science and Resources, 1999, p. 3; Innovation Summit Implementation Group, 2000; Love, 2000, 2000, 1998; Rothschild, undated; Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates, 2002; Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU, 2002 p. ii; The British Council, 2001).

Designing is the means by which new scientific knowledge is converted into real world outcomes (Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU, 2002). It is the operational foundation of knowledge-based economies because of its roles in the creation of innovative and competitive products, systems, services, government policies; business and organisational structures; enterprise-wide systems and procedures; information and communication management and transmission processes; financial products; economic strategies; and culturally-based processes. The effectiveness and efficiency of design processes impacts directly on the outcomes of business, industry, education, government and the not-for-profit sectors and, therefore on the likely success or otherwise of governments' economic and social plans (Freeman, 1995, p. 24).

The efficiency and effectiveness of a nation's design processes depends on its design infrastructure (Freeman, 1995; Friedman, 2000; Kim, 2002). This design infrastructure consists of the highly educated design professionals, design organisations, design industry associations, design education programs, venture capital for innovative projects, design research funding, and government policies and agencies aimed at maximising the benefits of design expertise across industry, government, education, and no-for-profit sectors.

This paper draws attention to problems in Australia's design infrastructure that compromise the very core of Australian government initiatives in:

- Innovation
- Reshaping Australia as a knowledge economy
- Attracting international investment
- The strategic management of Australia in relation to east, south, and south-east Asian and Pacific Rim countries.

After setting out key issues in relationships between designing, design infrastructure, innovation, the development of knowledge-based economies, the paper outlines Australia's current design infrastructure and describes how its weaknesses compromise plans for Australia's future. The paper concludes with suggestions for organisational and funding initiatives so that Australia's design infrastructure is able to provide the necessary support to realise the intended outcomes of Australian programs for economic and social development.

Key Conceptual Issues

The definition of 'design' used in this paper is that of Simon (1984) who regarded designing as the creating of a plan (design) to change existing situations into preferred ones. In the literature, the term 'design' is often used to refer to *anything* associated with designing. This epistemologically wider use, however, can be problematic. For example, 'design' might be used to refer to 'a Hyundai Excel car', but a customer would likely be unhappy if they received the specification for building that car (the design), rather than the car itself.

Design, innovation, knowledge economies, and economic and social development

Most developed countries have identified that their economic and social development depends on increased emphasis on the knowledge-related aspects of industry, commerce, service provision and governance (Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates, 2002; Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU, 2002). Developed countries cannot easily compete in manufacturing terms with developing countries that can offer lower labour costs, reduced environmental and health and safety costs, and low levels of attention to intellectual property (IP) protection legislation. What remains to developed countries for maintaining their economic advantage is leadership in the generation of knowledge by which new products and services are made or provided. That is, by converting new scientific knowledge through efficient and effective design processes undertaken by tertiary trained design professionals, design researchers and other intermediate professionals (e.g. marketing specialists) into real products, services, systems, programs, business strategies, organisational structures, policies and the like.

These knowledge economies, therefore, have two aspects:

- The knowledge conversion processes (designing) that result in accumulated practical knowledge (designs) for real products, services, systems, programs, policies etc.
- The knowledge generation processes (research) that result in accumulated theory knowledge that is of use in designing

Designing, therefore, has a key and irreplaceable role across national economic and social development in:

- The creation of design specifications manufacturing products or artefacts
- The design and planning of procedures and physical resources necessary or the provision of services
- The design of symbolic plans for new systems
- The design of processes and policies that shape new programs in for example, social services and education.

Designing, therefore, as the conversion of ideas and new knowledge into real world products, systems and services, offers a powerful and effective strategy for developing a knowledge-based economy. Building a nation's economic and social development on designing rather than research or invention is more efficient and effective in the current global economic scenario. In this scenario, where typical product life is less than three years and successful commercial exploitation is challenged within six months regardless of an invention's complexity – often by products that evade or compromise an invention's costly IP protection - focusing on invention, or on research to support invention (as IP), is relatively ineffective. Research in the UK shows innovation programs based on government investment in basic research undertaken by universities is not a strong platform for national economic and social development regardless of legislation aimed at IP protection (see, for example, Massey, 2001; Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU, 2002).

In these circumstances, investment in design expertise and infrastructure enables knowledge to be used and reused in the development of new products and services that provide local and national competitive advantage and which offer considerable benefits over 'single shot' products of invention. Increasing a nation's ability in designing offers a direct multiplier effect on investment in research because it increases the number of economically and socially valuable outcomes that can be created from each new research finding. For this reason, many developed and developing countries such as the US, the UK, Norway, Finland, Germany, Korea, Thailand have recognised that design expertise and infrastructure contribute very strongly to GDP, both directly and indirectly, though improving the efficiency and effectiveness of knowledge initiatives across sectors. For example, in the UK in 2001, UK businesses invested around AU\$72 billion in design activities (not including building the UK's design infrastructure) (Summers, 2001). In consequence, these countries have invested heavily in improving their design infrastructures to enable the effective utilisation of research-derived knowledge through design centres and futures-based initiatives such as the UK Foresight programs (see, for example, Arnold, Kuhlman, & Van der Meulen, 2001;

Freeman, 1995; Kim, 2002; Korvenmaa, 2000; National Science Foundation, 2001; Summers, 2001).

These gains from improving design infrastructure occur even when national research is not at the cutting edge because the potential of existing knowledge available in the public domain is not yet exhausted for designing world class products, services and systems that give economic and social advantage. An example is the US space program, which in the main has utilised traditional Newtonian mathematics and relied as much as possible on relatively 'old', but well-proven, knowledge (French, 1985).

Design Infrastructure Indicators

Comparing design infrastructure across nations is not straightforward. The human activity of designing impacts across a very wide range of human activities including: technical issues in the different forms of engineering; marketing and advertising issues relating to visual appearance of products or documentary representations of those products or services; visual and other representations that influence intangible perceptions about the characteristics of individuals, products and organisations (for example, through corporate image management, fashion, jewellery, furniture; design of social and educational services; policies procedures and other abstract models of systems), programs in information and communication technologies.

Research into the key characteristics of best practice in national innovation systems (Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU, 2002) points to the essential roles that designing plays. These key characteristics are:

- Business enterprises are the core of technology development as they provide both demand and supply
- A large part of innovation depends on the underlying structure of design and engineering activities rather than R&D
- Firms draw large proportions of their knowledge for their own technology development from other firms. These inter-firm knowledge interactions are critical to innovation
- In inter-firm knowledge flows, people are centrally important. Firms are creators of human capital
- In Asia, advanced countries have moved past a preceding phase when:
 - Scientific and technology capabilities were located in public institutions
 - Education and training institutions, rather than firms, undertook most development of technological skills and capabilities
- Successful innovation programs in advanced industrial countries is underpinned by dual public policy structure:

- Policy to strengthen technological learning, technological capabilities and innovative activities of firms
- Policies to strengthen the scientific, technological and training institutions undertaking activities on behalf of industrial firms (especially to improve their demand for improved technology)
- National management of interactions with multinational companies to strengthen local economies, and localisation of multinational companies' technological development activities.

Particularly significant is the understanding that a substantial part of innovation depends on designing rather than research and development.

The importance of design activity in innovation is often hidden or their benefits minimised because of the ways that innovation systems are measured. Clark and Guy (1997) points to the ways that design activity and design infrastructure are structurally excluded by the seven most common measures of innovative activity Table 1).

Table 1: Seven common measures of innovation activity (from Clark & Guy, 1997)

Measure of innovation	Weakness in assessing role of design infrastructure
Research and Development	Strongly underestimates small firms, design, production engineering and software (a design issue)
Patents	Misses software design
Significant innovations	Misses incremental design improvements
Expert Judgments	Judgements beyond expertise (problems in finding suitable multidisciplinary experts to judge complexities of design projects against innovations based on single disciplines)
Product Announcements	Misses in-house processes, innovations and product improvements (likely generated by design processes)
Technical Employees	Lack of homogeneity of qualifications (especially relevant in design disciplines where the neglect of design infrastructure in tertiary education (Bachelors to PhD) means that many professional designers are relatively less qualified than practitioners in other professional domains such as Medicine, Law or Engineering.
Actual vs. Predicted Market Values	Cannot distinguish innovation from other intangible assets, or from monopoly (as a factor in innovation, the benefits of design activities also cannot be distinguished by this approach)

Research Issues

Research to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of design activities is undertaken in four areas:

- Research into designing and design processes

- Research into the ways that humans perceive and use designed outcomes
- Research into designed outcomes themselves
- Research into how design activities and outcomes articulate with other human activities

Research into designing and design processes resulting in information about the human activity of designing. This includes research into the human active designing, to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of designers and design teams. It includes research to support designers by facilitating their mental and physiological processes, research into managing of activities associated with designing, research into, and literature about, ‘design processes’, and the historical study of designing and the theories about it

Research into the ways that humans perceive and use designed outcomes (products, systems, services, programs etc). This is user-based research, and includes human computer interaction, ergonomics, market-research and some aspects of anthropology.

Research resulting in information about designed outcomes and the contexts in which humans interact with designed outcomes. One of the main elements of this research is the study of design history, the outcomes of which (appropriately reworked) offer heuristics for designers to gain the benefits of experience drawn from previous design implementations. It includes research that supports the representation of prior knowledge in ways that assist designers find solutions to particular well-defined problems in a routine manner. This latter is essentially techno-informatic as its focus is the transformation of information about particular problem characteristics into information specifying the physical attributes of solutions that resolve them.

Research into how design activities and outcomes articulate with other human activities. This includes research into the interaction between design processes and other human activities such as business processes, and information about how designed outcomes mediate other human activities. It includes, for example, historical research into socio-cultural changes that result from the use of particular designed artefacts. It also includes research in different areas of business and public management that inform how design activities and designed outcomes can best be integrated with business, industrial, commercial and other processes and activities. The boundaries of this area of design research overlap substantially with other disciplines such as historical research because most human-made objects, services, activities etc. are in some way ‘designed’, and historically based socio-cultural analyses would be expected to include the effects of the use of particular technologies and artefacts in a situation being studied.

These four aspects of design research each make a distinct contribution to design infrastructure. The effectiveness of design research projects and their contribution to improving the efficiency and effectiveness of national design infrastructures remain, however, ultimately defined by:

- Levels of funding for design research
- The proportion of research undertaken specific to improving the efficiency and effectiveness of designing undertaken

- The effectiveness of dissemination of design research findings to industry, government agencies through, e.g. educational programs and peer reviewed journals and conferences
- Support for collaboration and articulation with other professional disciplines.

Australian Design Infrastructure

The government of Australia has policies that encourage innovation to support national economic and social development, and the transition from resource to knowledge economy (see, for example, Commonwealth of Australia, 2001; Dept of Industry Science and Resources, 1999, 1999; Innovation Summit Implementation Group, 2000). These are similar to initiatives found in most developed countries (see, for examples, Academy of Finland, 1997; Canadian Agri-Food Research Council, 1997; ISIG, 2000; Kim, 2002; Langrish, 1987; Marceau & Dodgson, 1999; National Science Foundation, 2001, 1998; Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates, 2002; The British Council, 2001; Whitney, n.d.).

There are strong indications, however, that weaknesses in Australia's design infrastructure, neglect of professional design expertise, over emphasis on research and invention, and relative blindness to the key roles of designing across all aspects of Australian economic and social development are seriously compromising Australian innovation policies and plans for becoming a 'knowledge nation'.

Weaknesses in Product Design

The history of research and development in Australia indicate that product development has been mainly undertaken without accessing the benefits of professional design expertise. Instead Australia has relied mainly on ad-hoc processes of invention and 'trial and error' (see, for example, Boardman, 2001; Freeman, 1995; Hartley, 1994). The significant commercial and social benefits of utilising product design professionals have been ignored. Instead, Australian design activities have mainly been undertaken by individuals without bachelors, masters or doctoral qualifications in designing: often engineers and business professionals who have needed products to sell, or researchers demonstrating practical application of new research findings. This issue underpins the relatively low levels of new Australian designed products and innovation outcomes, lack of manufacturing infrastructure, weaknesses in urban and industrial planning – particularly where it involves public participation in planning processes, an insubstantial product design infrastructure, a relative imbalance of visual design education over product design education. It is of concern that existing and proposed Australian innovation policies continue down this ad-hoc path (see, for example, Commonwealth of Australia, 2001; Department of Industry Science and Resources, 2001; Dept of Industry Science and Resources, 1999; Group of Eight - Australia's Leading Universities, 2000; Innovation Summit Implementation Group, 2000; Kemp, 1999; Sara, 2000).

Neglect of Professional Design Expertise

Australian lack of awareness, or neglect, of the role of professional design expertise and knowledge based on quality tertiary education in designing through Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral education programs emerges in many ways:

- Awareness of and support for professional product design is absent from government literature on innovation
- Almost complete absence of product design from Australian business consultants' models of innovation. The consequence is that consultants do not appropriately advise their clients to gain the benefits from employing product design expertise or to integrate this expertise into the necessary stages in their innovation processes.
- Lack of awareness of product design issues in major Australian organisations. This reduces the opportunities to increase the number of successful products reaching the market. Those that do are likely to have a reduced marketability and market acceptance.
- Confusion and mal-investment in research sectors due to underlying assumptions that researchers will produce designs for products as well as research findings
- Confusion and mal-investment in entrepreneurial sectors due to expectations that researchers will produce fully fledged product designs, or that entrepreneurs themselves will convert research findings into products. Neither gains the significant and evidenced benefits of professional product design services whose purpose is the design of successful marketable products that fit specific business, research, manufacturing marketing and customer contexts.
- Weakness in Australia's design sectors (particularly product and emerging design sectors) because there is a lower than expected demand for their services.
- Lack of balance in tertiary design education across Australia because focusing on business and neglecting design results in an emphasis on selling "image" rather than developing products. In turn this emerges as an infrastructure imbalance towards graphics design industries rather than product and services design industries.
- Almost complete absence of design research centres in Australia. This reflects both the lack of awareness of the direct contribution of design research to economic development, and the shortfall in design education programs in the product design and engineering design sectors (on which design research centres are usually based).
- Absence of a government agency similar to the Design Policy Unit in the UK, whose role is solely to direct and manage the development of Australia's design infrastructure and government programs in, for example, design research, design education, industry awareness of design issues and Australian export promotion.
- Serious concerns about the quality of Australian design education in areas ranging from engineering design through to graphic design (see, for example, Swann & Young, 2000)](Beder, 1993; Love, 1999; Svensson, 1981; Wray, 1992)

Historical Factors

In part, weakness in Australia's design infrastructure can be explained by Australia's history. Australia's recent past as a colony, its economic dependence on the exploitation of resources, its low population and its technological isolation and technological dependence on the US, UK, Scandinavia, Korea and other developed countries, are factors that have broadly shaped its industrial, educational, government and design infrastructures without requiring a strong Australian design infrastructure. The significant weaknesses in Australia's design infrastructure reflect Australia's role as a colony whose primary purpose was to benefit Britain. This role limited the development of design and technology facilities that would enable Australia to compete directly with Britain in world markets. An example is the joint British-Australian program of wool research in which the design and research for new wool products and manufacturing processes was undertaken only in Britain with Australian researchers focusing on improving wool production (Boardman, 2001). A logical

consequence of these historic factors is blindness in Australia to the need for a strong design infrastructure. This has resulted in its substitution by weaker alternatives such as: a culture of individual inventors creating products specific to Australian situations (mainly based on components designed elsewhere); overemphasis on research; and an over-dependence on visual design activities (graphic design, multimedia design etc) in an attempt to make up for the lack of adequate product/service design infrastructure by increased marketing and advertising effort. This latter is reflected in higher proportions of graphic designers to product designers in Australia.

Partial Design Process

A dominant characteristic of designing in Australia is the use of partial design processes, in which Australian designers create designs that consist mainly of assemblies of components or ideas designed elsewhere (usually overseas) (see, for example, Svensson, 1981). This approach to designing is limited in the benefits it can offer compared to undertaking designing 'from the ground up'. An example of the innovation limitations of this Australian design style is the experience of product designer recently arrived from the UK. He contacted a major bearing supplier in Western Australia for a catalogue - an essential resource in designing new mechanical devices - and was told that they did not supply them. 'There is no need', he was informed, because 'if they could be told what machine the bearing came from they would get a replacement'. This cameo reflects an attitude that innovative designing is done overseas, and results in limited support for Australian designers designing innovative solutions. It results in reduced numbers of fully designed products, and hence reduced numbers of successful Australian-designed outcomes.

Design not Invention

A consequence of the previously mentioned factors is an overemphasis of the role of individual acts of invention in Australian initiatives aimed at improving innovation and a knowledge-based economy. Invention is the dominant Australian approach to gaining commercial advantage through innovation and results in a limited number of single items of protected intellectual property, such as the Hill's hoist, the black box flight recorder, or the fridge. This is the opposite of what is required for a knowledge economy based on the rich and broad-based generation of designs for multiple economically and socially valuable products, systems and services. This emphasis on invention rather design is widespread in the Australian innovation literature(see, for example, Baddeley, 2002)](Department of Industry Science and Resources, 2001). It is problematic because the number and type of outcomes are restricted compared to those produced by design processes, and the development of design infrastructure is reduced because the skills of invention are a limited subset of the skills needed for designing.

Design and R & D

The concept of Research and Development' (R&D) has become redefined in Australia reflecting Australia's weakness in design infrastructure. The concept of 'R&D' makes good sense in, e.g., UK and US contexts because they have well-established and functional design infrastructures.

In these contexts, 'development' in R&D refers to practical 'clinical' or 'applied' research in support of design activities. For example, in pressure vessel design, the role of the

development aspect of R&D is applied research aimed at improving pressure vessel designed outcomes relating to, e.g., form factors, stress, creep, material condition and failure modes. This development research provides support to pressure vessel designers by providing more reliable heuristics and theory models for designers to utilise in creating new pressure vessel designs. The ‘development’ aspect of R&D results in support for designing: it is not itself designing.

There is confusion on this difference between designing and ‘development’ research in Australia. The lack of adequate design infrastructure in Australia has led to an assumption that product design happens as part of the development aspect of R&D Development. It is a similar confusion to lack of differentiation between research and designing that results in the assumption that product design is undertaken by researchers – regardless of their obvious lack of formal training in design skills.

Fragmentation in Australia's Design Infrastructure

Design infrastructure in Australia is not only weak it is also fragmented. Several factors are involved:

- Colonial influences that for many years discouraged Australia from developing the design infrastructure that would enable its independence through designing and manufacturing high-value products. This has led to the acceptable areas of design infrastructure being developed whilst less acceptable areas were not (e.g. resulting in the over emphasis of graphics/typography and associated programs in Australian design education programs).
- Bureaucratic segmentation in which Federal parliament is responsible for the international aspects of design processes such as exports, and State and Territory parliaments are responsible for managing local industry.
- Lack of a centralised national government sponsored body whose main duty is to build and manage the national design infrastructure necessary for Australia’s economic and social development
- A lack of awareness across sectors of the significant benefits of professional design skills and design organisations in the designing new products and services.
- Friction between different sub-fields of design.

Fragmentation of design infrastructure is an important issue because contemporary design projects increasingly depend on multidisciplinary aspects of design infrastructure; involve services as well as products; and are often co-joined with documentation, image, branding, business process redesign, and manufacturing system design. For the outcomes of complex design projects be satisfactory requires numerous inputs from the various design fields to be well integrated into a coherent solution. In the longer term, this requires the development of much more complex methodics for cross/inter and multi-disciplinary design processes. In the short-term, however, it requires over arching institutional arrangements to encourage the integration of these different elements of design infrastructure.

There have been attempts to resolve divisions in the design field through aggregation of sub-groups under the banner of the Design Institute of Australia (DIA). There remains, however, a serious cultural gap between the more technical design disciplines (represented by e.g. the Institution of Engineers Australia (IEAust) and software institutions such as the Australian Computer Society (ACS)) and the design disciplines represented by e.g. the Design Institute of Australia. At this stage, however, there do not seem to be any significant factors acting on the major Australian design institutions such as the DIA, IEAust and the ACS to collaborate, and to actively support and develop emerging design sub-fields.

New Design Fields

There are three broad fields of design expertise:

- Technical design such as engineering, computer, communications and information systems, and business process design.
- Visually based design such as graphics, image management, fashion whose origins lie in the Art and Craft traditions.
- Emerging design fields in which embedded design activities are often hidden in other disciplines. These emerging design fields are not yet widely regarded as design sub-disciplines. They include, for example: social program design, educational program design, government policy design, and business strategy design.

Professionals in these emerging design sub-fields are involved in ‘devising courses of action to change present situations to preferred situations’ but in many cases their work is not yet widely viewed as designing. There is a slow evolution by which these emerging design disciplines become noticed, associated with more established design disciplines, and later acquire status as sub-fields of design in their own right. Design fields that have already followed this path include: communications design, human computer interface design, document design, and packaging design. These emerging design sub-fields were identified as important aspects of design infrastructure by the Australian National Design Review (Freeman, 1995).

In terms of building coherent design infrastructure that includes these new design fields, Australia lags behind other developed countries such as Japan, the UK and the USA where institutional bridges are being made between technical and ‘Art and Craft design disciplines’ and emerging design fields. For example, in the UK there are alliances between engineering and art departments of universities such as Glasgow. In the USA, there are Xerox programs in which scientists and artists work together in pairs. In Germany, the engineering-based WDK design movement has transformed itself into the ‘Design Society’ to include all design disciplines.

Cultural Barriers

The business practices necessary for successful complex design disciplines processes that involve collaborative multidisciplinary teamwork, are at odds with Australian business models that encourage the development of highly specialist niche business initiatives.

Building design infrastructure relating to emerging design disciplines requires addressing problems facing any new professional design field. That is, the professional practices of these emerging design fields are hidden, subsumed, within other fields of practice. For example, government policy design is currently widely conflated with policy analysis in spite of the latter being an area whose analyses are post-facto and consequently a very different field of practice.

Resolving Australia's Design Infrastructure Problems

A strong design infrastructure is a key element of successful national policies and programs aimed at gaining the benefits for Australians of a knowledge-based economy leading to economic and social development. There are strong indications on many fronts that weaknesses in Australia's design infrastructure compromise Australian initiatives in innovation and in building a knowledge-based economy.

Many of Australia's design infrastructure problems, however, have been faced at some time, and overcome, by most developed and many developing countries (see, for example, Kim, 2002; Korvenmaa, 2000; Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU, 2002). Most of these countries have addressed these design infrastructure issues successfully to add significant benefits to their economic and social development programs through innovation and the use of design activities as an effective practical basis for transition towards them establishing knowledge-based economies. The approaches that these successful countries have used have been similar, and offer a well-mapped pathway of successful initiatives for building Australia's design infrastructure. The UK in particular shows how relatively recent changes in organisational elements and funding arrangements at government, non-government and educational levels have provided a framework around which existing and new elements of design infrastructure have coalesced with very significant positive economic and social impacts. Building Australian design infrastructure from its low base means that problems identified in the development of the other countries design infrastructure are open to being corrected. Australia not only has the opportunity to implement new structures and organisations to build a world-class design infrastructure. It also has the opportunity to establish the seeds of institutional change that will help resolve issues relating to design and innovation that are embedded in existing institutional cultures.

Countries such as the UK, the US, Finland and Korea that have been effective in building design infrastructures to successfully leverage investment in research and business have done so through an extended program involving the establishment of a number of formal institutions whose primary roles are design research, design promotion, strategic support for industry through design, and tertiary education of multidisciplinary design practitioners and design project managers. Practical examples of this in Australia would be to:

- Establish Design Centres in major cities
- Establish government design policy units
- Develop formal mechanisms for funding and supporting multi-disciplinary design research and design education programs

A key factor is improvements to the tertiary education of designers because of its role in providing sufficient numbers of highly skilled and educated designers and design managers capable of working across disciplines. In countries such as the US and UK, design graduates

of Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral programs are key knowledge workers. Doctoral students in Design and postdoctoral design researchers provide the basic research into design processes that improve the efficiency and effectiveness of design teams and organisations in knowledge conversion.

According to Clark and Guy (1997, pp. 38-39), the most appropriate approach for governments to undertake is incremental. That is, implementing policy, evaluating outcomes, retaining policies and programs that show promise and discarding those that do not. They argue that small to medium enterprises require special attention in encouraging innovation because of the specific scale-based factors that require external support (Clark & Guy, 1997, pp. 35-36). Through the 1980s and 1990s, the UK has successfully implemented several such programs, e.g. providing financial support for SMEs to draw on external expertise from design professionals, making available examples of successful use of design in a variety of business circumstances, providing programs drawing attention to the financial and competitive benefits to SMEs investing in design, supporting a government agency (the Design Policy Unit) and a public organisation (the Design Council) to manage national resources in and through design activities in a very wide range of disciplines and professions.

References

Academy of Finland. (1997). *National Strategy for Centres of Excellence in Research*. Helsinki: EDITA.

Arnold, E., Kuhlman, S., & Van der Meulen, B. (2001). *A Singular Council. Evaluation of the Research Council of Norway*, [html document]. Technopolis. Available: www.technopolis.co.uk/reports/RCN/RCN_synthesis.pdf.

Baddeley, A. (2002). *Australian Inventions*, [html document]. Available: www.maths.uwa.edu.au/~adrian/ozinvent.html.

Beder, S. (1993). Making Engineering Design Sustainable. *Transactions of the Institution of Engineers, Australia; Multi-Disciplinary Engineering*, 17(1), 31-35.

Boardman, K. (2001). *Science and Innovation Centenary Article*, [html document]. Australian Bureau of Statistics. Available: www.abs.gov.au.

Canadian Agri-Food Research Council. (1997). *Canada's National Strategy for Agri-Food Research and Technology Transfer 1997-2002*, [html document]. Canadian Agri-Food Research Council. Available: www.carc-crac.ca/english/national_strategy/strge.htm [2001, Sept].

Clark, J., & Guy, K. (1997). *Innovation and Competitiveness*. Brighton, UK: Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates,.

Commonwealth of Australia. (2001). *Backing Australia's Ability - An Innovation Action Plan for the Future*. Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia.

Department of Industry Science and Resources. (2001). *Introduction: Innovation and Opportunity*, [html document]. Australian Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. Available: <http://www.dfat.gov.au/facts/innovative/fs01.html>.

Dept of Industry Science and Resources. (1999). *Shaping Australia's Future. Innovation - Framework Paper*. Canberra: DISR.

Dept of Industry Science and Resources. (1999). *Innovation Policy*. Canberra: DISR.

Freeman, D. (1995). *Competing by Design: The National Design Review Report*. Australian Academy of Design. Sydney: National Design Review Steering Committee.

French, M. J. (1985). *Conceptual Design for Engineers* (2nd ed.). London: Design Council.

Friedman, K. (2000). Creating Design Knowledge: From Research into Practice, *IDATER 2000* (pp. 5-31). Loughborough: IDATER.

Group of Eight - Australia's Leading Universities. (2000). *Research & Innovation: Australia's Future*. Manuka, ACT: Group of Eight - Australia's Leading Universities.

Hartley, R. G. (1994). *Industry and Infrastructure in Western Australia 1829-1970*. Perth: IEAust and Heritage Council of WA.

Innovation Summit Implementation Group. (2000). *Innovation - Unlocking the Future. Final Report of the Innovation Summit Implementation Group*. Canberra: ISR.

ISIG. (2000). *Elements of National Innovation Systems - International Ratings. ISIG Information Paper IV*, [word document]. Innovation Policy Branch, DISR. Available: <http://www.isr.gov.au/industry/innovation/4ConstraintsOnAustInnov.doc>.

Kemp, D. (1999). *Knowledge and Innovation: A policy statement on research and research training*. Canberra: Legislative Services, AusInfo.

Kim, D. (2002). *Korea Design Policy*, [html document]. Korean Institute of Design Promotion. Available: www.designdb.com/english/kidp/policy.html.

Korvenmaa, P. (2000). Design Research and the Wealth of Nations. Reflections on the interaction of design research and national policies of research, innovation and industry. In D. Durling & K. Friedman (Eds.), *Doctoral Education in Design: Foundations for the Future* (pp. 447-452). Stoke-on-Trent: Staffordshire University Press.

Langrish, J. (1987). *The Importance of Design in Technology Transfer*. Manchester: Inst of Advanced Studies, Manchester Metropolitan University.

Love, T. (1998). *Social, Environmental and Ethical Factors in Engineering Design Theory: a Post-positivist Approach*. Perth, Western Australia: Praxis Education.

Love, T. (1999). Engineering design education: some implications of a post-positivist theory of design cognition. In N. Juster (Ed.), *The Continuum of Design Education* (pp. 33-42). Bury St Edmunds, UK: Professional Engineering Publishing Ltd.

Love, T. (2000). Educating those involved in changing human futures: a more coherent programme for design education. In C. Swann & E. Young (Eds.), *Re-inventing Design Education in the University* (pp. 242-248). Perth: School of Design, Curtin University of Technology.

Love, T. (2000). New roles for design education in university settings. In C. Swann & E. Young (Eds.), *Re-inventing Design Education in the University* (pp. 249-255). Perth: School of Design, Curtin University of Technology.

Marceau, J., & Dodgson, M. (1999). *Systems of Innovation*. DISR. Available: <http://www.isr.gov.au/industry/innovation/Framework1.pdf>.

Massey, S. (2001). *Comparative Study of Systems of IP Management in HEIs in the UK, USA and Germany*, [html document]. Available: <http://info.sm.umist.ac.uk/esrcip/Projects/L5253022/Final%20Report.htm>.

National Science Foundation. (1998). *Norway's Science Policy*, [html document]. National Science Foundation. Available: www.nsf.gov/home/int/europe/reports/98.htm [2001, July].

National Science Foundation. (2001). *NSF GPRA Strategic Plan FY 2001-2006: IV. Strategy*, [html document]. National Science Foundation. Available: www.nsf.gov/pubs/2001/nsf0104/strategy.htm [2001, Sept].

National Science Foundation. (2001). *NSF GPRA Strategic Plan FY 2001-2006: III. Outcome Goals: Investing in today's promise for tomorrow's achievement*, [html document]. National Science Foundation. Available: www.nsf.gov/pubs/2001/nsf0104/outcome.htm [2001, Sept].

Owen, I. (1990). Building Your Business on Design. In K. Barnfather (Ed.), *Directory of Designers*. London: The Design Council.

Rothschild, E. E. (undated). *Investing in Design*. Melbourne: The Design Council of Australia.

Sara, V. (2000). *ARC Our Vision*, [html document]. Australian Research Council. Available: http://www.arc.gov.au/strat_plan/vision.htm [2002].

Simon, H. A. (1984). *The Sciences of the Artificial* (2nd ed.). Cambridge, Ma: MIT Press.

Summers, A. (2001). *Facts and Figures on Design in Britain*, [html document]. Design Council UK. Available: <http://www.design-council.org.uk/design/content/publication.jsp?contentID=09009e0d80044b22>.

Svensson, N. L. (1981). Engineering Design in Australia. In V. Hubka & W. E. Eder (Eds.), *Schriftenreihe WDK 7 Results of ICED '81 (Rome)*. Zurich: Heurista.

Swann, C., & Young, E. (Eds.). (2000). *Re-inventing Design Education in the University, Conference Proceedings*. Perth: Curtin University of Technology.

Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates. (2002). *Technopolis Projects: The Rest of Europe*, [html document]. Technopolis. Available: www.technopolis.co.uk/projects/europe.htm.

Technopolis Innovation Policy Research Associates CENTRIM & SPRU. (2002). *Overall Policy Framework and the Development of the Industrial Innovation System (Vol1)*, [html document]. Technopolis. Available: www.technopolis.co.uk/reports/201VOL1.

The British Council. (2001). *Innovation UK: Science, Wealth Creation and Social Well-being in Britain*. The British Council. Available: <http://www.britishcouncil.org/science/science/pubs/innovations.pdf>.

Whitney, D. E. (n.d.). *The U.K Government Program in Engineering Design Research*, [html document]. MIT. Available: www.mit.edu/ctpid/www/Whitney/Europe/hills1.html [2002].

Wray, G. (1992). *Attaining competence in engineering design at undergraduate level: educational differences between engineering and engineering science* (Public Lecture). Perth, WA: Dept of Mechanical and Materials Engineering University of Western Australia.

Bio

Dr. Terence Love is design researcher and designer whose interests focus on the practicalities of improving design activities and outcomes across the breadth of human endeavour. At this time, he works for Edith Cowan University at the We-B Research Centre and as an adjunct to the School of Design at Curtin University. His current research is in identifying context specific attributes and strategies by which Design Centres successfully contribute to innovation processes, to the building of a knowledge-based economy, to improving national economic and social development outcomes, and in identifying combinations of product design, information systems (IS) design, and organisation design processes to minimise rework and design failures.